

CONTEXTUALIZED TEACHING AND LEARNING STRATEGY (CTL): ITS IMPACT TO THE STUDENTS' MATHEMATICAL ENGAGEMENT AND PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

The current health emergency where education is delivered through distance learning modality, affected by the will to stimulate learning when the students are at home since those who are struggling in Mathematics tells that the subject is difficult and hard to deal with gave rise to the realization of this study. The purpose of the study was to determine the impact of Contextualized Teaching and Learning Strategy (CTL) on the student's mathematical engagement and problem-solving skills of select Grade 7 students of Quezon National High School during the academic year 2020 - 2021. Descriptive-Experimental design was utilized in the study participated by thirty-five (35) STE-Constellation's students. A teacher made pretest, posttest and survey questionnaires on the perception of CTL and student engagement was utilized. Mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentages, t-test for dependent data, Pearson product moment of correlation and stepwise multiple linear regression were the statistical treatments used. Based on the findings, majority of the students strongly agreed that exposure to CTL displays higher level of student engagement and clearly shows that the students are being encouraged by the teaching practice, authentic situated learning activities and communities of practice used during Virtual Mathematics classes. There was a significant difference between the pretest and post test scores performance, implying that the students were able to improve their problem-solving skills. In addition, a positive significant relationship was recorded and the improvement of respondents in applying what they learned is due to the higher engagement. With these implications in the educative process, teachers are highly recommended to include CTL in class program or lesson planning as additional reinforcing tool in teaching. It also recommends that, the students may be given contextualized activities either individual or group learning tasks to enhance their mathematical engagement and problem-solving skills.

Keywords: Contextualized Teaching and Learning Strategy, Student Engagement, Problem Solving Skills, Virtual Classroom